

Gemstone Occurrences of Nanyaseik Area, Phakant Township, Kachin State

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Abstract

The primary occurrences of gemstones in Nanyaseik area seem to be scarce, the secondary placer gem-bearing deposits are noteworthy. All gemstone occurrences from Nanyaseik area are mainly recovered from secondary deposits (gravels). Gemstones are found as detrital fragments in gem-bearing soil horizons known as byones. According to the drainage characteristics of this area and its environs gem-bearing alluvium had been probably descended from northwestern and western watersheds that created those secondary deposits, especially at the junctions of major streams and their tributaries where local people wash the byone and extract gems. These gems include precious rubies, sapphires (including padparadscha) and others; spinel, tourmaline, zircon, quartz, diopside and almandine garnet.

Key words: Nanyaseik area, secondary deposits, Phakant Township, byones, Kachin State

Introduction

Nanyaseik area is situated in Phakant Township, Myitkyina District, Kachin State (Northern Myanmar). It is bounded by Latitudes 25° 36' to 25° 43' N and Longitudes 96° 30' to 96° 36' E in one inch topographic map index of 92 C/10. The total areal coverage is about 130 square kilometers of mountainous and rugged terrain (Fig - 1,2,3).

There is no in situ in order to find of gemstones. So, the secondary placer gem-bearing deposits are of economic interest. Gemstone mining using both open pit mining method and square pit mining method. Some gemstones may be freed from the various softer parent rock by weathering, eroded, transported, deposited and accumulated in the adjacent valleys and flat lowland areas. The gem materials are associated with other rock forming minerals in the gravels. The gem bearing gravel beds are called byone layers in which ruby, sapphire, spinel, zircon, tourmaline, quartz, diopside and almandine garnet are found.

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Fig - (1) Location Map of Nanyaseik Area

Fig - (2) Satellite image of the Nanyaseik Area

Fig - (3) Geomorphology of the Nanyaseik Area (Three dimensional view)

Scope and Objectives

The present research aims to -

- (a) study the gem occurrences in Nanyaseik area.
- (b) carry out laboratory works including mineralogical studies and identification of gemstones.
- (c) study the quality of gemstones in comparison with those of Mogok Stone Tract in the hope of gaining attention of mineralogists, gemmologists, geologists, other gem dealers and gem collectors.

Mining Methods

Mechanisation is used wherever possible to ensure profitable yield. Mining methods applied in Nanyaseik area are as follows:

1. Open pit mining method (Inn Bye) (Fig - 4)
2. Square pit mining method (Lebin Twin) (Fig - 5)

Fig - (4) An open pit mine
(alluvial placers working)
at Gem City Worksite

Loc: N 25° 39' 33.6", E 96° 33' 11.2"

Fig - (5) Typical square pits in
Ko Naing Worksite

Loc: N 25° 41' 34.2", E 96° 32' 25.1"

1. Open Pit Mining Method (Inn Bye)

This method is mainly applied on secondary deposits. Almost all the mining activities in Nanyaseik area are carried out by means of this method for voluminous deposits. The mining operations involve:

- (a) Removing the overburden
- (b) Excavation of gem bearing gravel
- (c) Sluicing techniques

(a) Removing the overburden

The removal of overburden is carried out aided by bulldozers where the top soil is removed until gem bearing gravels (byones) exposed.

(b) Excavation of gem bearing gravels

It is carried out by means of excavators.

(c) Sluicing techniques

This sluicing method is very popular and carried throughout the year. It commonly applied on hillsides and steep valleys. It is an open trench method, local people called Myaw-dwin which are being sluiced by making use of water power that drains from the higher levels. The water supply is very important, conventionally by passing it along suitably cut bamboos or by water pipes operated by diesel engines. The top soil is first removed until the byone layer is exposed. The byones are then washed on a nearby flat circular floor. Water is diverted into it along with the byone in the form of sprays and the washed up materials enter the trailing canal and the heavy materials are trapped in pits or sluices.

2. Square Pit Mining Method (Lebin Twin)

There are about three thousands of old and current square pits at Nanyaseik area. It is a small square pit about four square feet. The depth may vary from (5-20) feet depending on the byone layer and bed rock.

Gem Worksites

In Nanyaseik area, the workable gem worksites are mostly situated in the western environs of Nanyaseik village. These worksites are generally N-S trending. Mine area extends about 8 km in NS, 5 km in EW directions. Based on the field evidences, rubies and other gemstones in Nanyaseik area are originated in marbles, and associated igneous rocks. However, gemstones are extracted from byones, secondary deposits (gravels) rather than from *insitu* (primary deposits). Notably five gem worksites are outstanding and are listed below (Fig - 6).

1. Khaing Kyin worksite (N 25° 41' 34.2" / E 96° 32' 25.1")
2. Lakha worksite (N 25° 38' 42.2" / E 96° 33' 17.6")
3. Sabaw worksite (N 25° 39' 38.1" / E 96° 32' 52.9")
4. Manaw worksite (N 25° 37' 25.5" / E 96° 32' 44.5")
5. Warphu worksite (N 25° 38' 25.8" / E 96° 32' 59.4")

Essential products of these gem worksites are primarily ruby and other semi-precious stones like tourmaline, spinel, garnet, zircon, quartz, etc. The above gem worksites work under the authority of Myanmar Gem Enterprise, Ministry of Mines. Annually workable period is only in dry season because of the heavy rainfall and swampy conditions in rainy season. Some gemologists stated that rubies and other precious stones are obtained from the alluvial deposits north of the village which are more productive than those to the south. These gemstones were derived from the detritus, afforded by the disintegration of crystalline limestones adjacent to the intrusive masses of granite.

Fig - (6) Map showing gemstone workings in Nanyaseik area (Htin Lynn Aung, 2011)

1. Khaing Kyin Worksite

The Khaing Kyin Worksite is situated in the northern most part of the study area. Owned by Ko Naing (a local people) uses a square pit mining method (Fig - 7). It is quite small, about three square feet, locally called Lebin twin (N 25° 41' 34.2" and E 96° 32' 25.1"). The depth reaches to twenty five feet, producing only ruby and other gemstones. The workable period is lasts only about five months producing about thirty carats of gem quality stones (Fig - 8, 9 & 10).

Ko Naing Worksite Loc: N 25° 41' 34.2", E 96° 32' 25.1"

Fig - (7) A square pit (Lebin Twin)

Fig - (8) Byones in a wooden tank ready for washing

Fig - (9) Washing and sieving byones in search of rubies

Fig - (10) Rubies sorted out from the byones

2. Lakha Worksite

The Lakha Worksite is close to the Warphu Worksite. In this worksite, local people (Ko Ahpha) used an open pit mining technique (Inn bye method) (Fig - 11). Basement rock (host rock) is NE dipping gneiss which shows reddish brown colour on weathered surfaces. The reddish brown soil cover is ten feet thick. Feldspars are mostly weathered and altered to clay (sticky mud). At this worksite, rubies and other associated gemstones are recovered from secondary placer deposits (Fig - 12).

Lakha Worksite Loc: N 25° 38' 42.2" , E 96° 33' 17.6"

Fig - (11) Recovery of byones by pulling process

Fig - (12) Sorted out gem quality rubies

3. Sabaw Worksite

The Sabaw Worksite lies in the central part of the Nanyaseik area. The office of Myanma Gem Enterprise, Ministry of Mines is situated at Sabaw village (N 25° 39' 38.1" / E 96° 32' 52.9").

4. Manaw Worksite

The Manaw Worksite is situated in the southern most part of the study area. Local people said that it was a famous worksite prior to the Sabaw Worksite.

5. Warphu Worksite

The Warphu Worksite is next to Lakha Worksite. Out of three mining companies, only two are at work, namely Sai Khay Company (N 25° 38' 25.8" / E 96° 32' 59.4") (Fig - 13) and Hlan Hlann Company (N 25° 38' 29.7" / E 96° 32' 36.0") (Fig - 15&16) where the former Palaung National Company (N 25° 38' 34.7" / E 96° 32' 26.7") came to a halt. The working two mining companies use open pit technique to extract rubies and other gemstones. At Sai Khay Company, gold particles can be seen on wooden pan (Fig - 14). During my field trip, Hlan Hlann company got a ruby crystal from byone at this time of investigation.

Sai Khay Worksite Loc : N 25° 38'25.8" , E 96° 32' 59.4"

Fig - (13) Recovery of byones by water sluicing method

Fig - (14) Gold particles

Hlan Hlann Worksite Loc: N 25° 38' 29.7", E 96° 32' 36.0"

Fig - (15) Washing and sieving byones

Fig - (16) Searching rubies from the byones

Nature of Secondary Deposits (gravels) and Gemstone Association

All gemstone occurrences from Nanyaseik area are mainly recovered from secondary deposits (gravels). Gemstones are found as detrital fragments in gem bearing soil horizons known as byones. The maximum depth of byone is very shallow, never exceeds one hundred feet. In some places, byones have been found within the reach of one foot depth from the surface. The soil type of byone is dominantly residual soil (laterite) overlying marbles. The thickness of soil ranges from 50' to 70'. In Nanyaseik area, basic soil profile succession can be listed as follows:

- Recent yellow to brown sandy and clayey soil mixed with gravels
- Bluish soil with organic matters
- Laterite and lateritic soil

Weathered laterite and lateritic soil are common to all gem worksites and are mostly formed as the lower most part with well developed byone horizons mixed with fragments of parent rocks occasionally and other soil types. The thickness of residual soil varies from a few inches to (10-20) feet.

Most of the workable gem worksites in Nanyaseik area applied open pit mining method due to the swampy lowland with very gentle slopes (5°-10°). Moreover, hydraulic sluicing, gravel pumping and vibration jiggling methods are also practiced to recover the gems which include ruby and other precious gemstones like sapphire, spinel, garnet, diopside, zircon, tourmaline, quartz, etc from byones. Finally these gems are sorted out by hand with tweezers. Inferior quality gemstones are also encountered in byones, elsewhere in gem worksites within shallow depths. Economically important, thick byone formations have not yet been found. In some places, opaque rubies, carbolates, as the native miners call (due to its resemblance to carbolic-soap) are also to be observed.

According to DGSE's staff report (1995), they examined the Nanyaseik area and stated that rubies and some assorted gemstones were obtained from the detritus, disintegration of crystalline limestones surrounded by intrusive body. They described five major localities in the environs of Nanyaseik area and show the production rate of rubies with their respective worksites as follows:

No.	Name of worksite	Product rate (ct/cubic yard)	Reserve JV worksite	Permitted JV worksite
1	Khaing Kyin Worksite MAPANYA-C-168802	Test pit - 2.5 Loodwin - 12.5	121 Blocks	3 Blocks
2	Sabaw Worksite MAPANYA-C-180780	1.2	12 Blocks	-
3	Warphu Worksite MAPANYA-C-180741	2.4	102 Blocks	-
4	Manaw Worksite MAPANYA-C-180720	1.2	40 Blocks	-
5	Maklain Worksite MAPANYA-C-210710	1.4	33 Blocks	-
			308 Blocks	

Conclusively, topographic features of the study area have not been a favourable site to form considerable thickness of gem bearing gravels (byones).

Fig - (17) Gem bearing gravels sandwiched in between gneiss (bed rock) and old stream sediments
(Myanmar Htun Worksite)

Loc: N 25° 39' 17.8" , E 96° 33' 04.6"

Fig - (18) Gem bearing pebbly layer sandwiched in between soil and laterite (Zabu Kyaw Aung Worksite)

Loc: N 25° 37' 07.1" , E 96° 32' 50.1"

Conclusion

All gemstone occurrences from Nanyaseik area are mainly recovered from secondary deposits (gravels). These are transported, deposited and accumulated in the adjacent valleys and flat lowland areas. Ruby, sapphire, spinel, zircon, tourmaline, quartz, garnet, diopside and other precious stones are extracted from byones, gem bearing gravels.

Future prospects

This research work is not the end of the story of gems occurrences of Nanya Stone Tract. Some more concealed gemstones could be discovered in the near future by local people, geologists, gemmologists, gems dealers and gems collectors.

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